

Brightspot & Selected Policy Instrument Assessment

Q1-4 only applicable to brightspot assessment.

1. Preliminaries

To be copied from brightspot spreadsheet

- ID
- DOI
- Title
- Authors
- Publication
- Category brightspot

2. Exclusion/Inclusion

Yes/No; If "No" for any of the three questions below, no further coding needed.

- Are there any policy instruments or support tools associated with this case?
- Is there evidence for diverse value approaches concerning this case?
- Is there evidence for elements of transformative governance?

Further coding to be applied to the Brightspot cases that are included based on the previous questions.